

Model Of Regional Public Service Implementation : Study Of Innovation Of The City Government Of Surabaya

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 03, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 04, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Public Service, City Government, Innovation</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6329785</p>	<p><i>This article discusses the implementation of public services with an innovative approach carried out by the Surabaya City Government. The research method uses a qualitative case study design approach, the research steps carried out are identifying the existence of an innovation program in the implementation of public services in the Surabaya City Government through online and print media and analysis of primary and secondary data obtained from data findings in the field. The results show that the Surabaya City Government has carried out innovation programs including 1) "Cak Emus" innovation program 2) "TAHU PANAS" innovation program 3) Economic Heroes and Young Fighters innovation program 4) "6 in 1" public service innovation program. Recommendations given The Surabaya City Government is expected to always make new innovations in line with the high demands of the community for excellent public services, and must always increase community involvement in the process of providing public services.</i></p>

Introduction

The form of application of democratic values after the reformation period in Indonesia, including the implementation through autonomy to the regions since 1999. The regional autonomy schedule has entered a new session in the direction of the enactment of Law Number 22 of 1999 concerning Regional Government which was subsequently revised by Law Number 32 of 2004, then revised by Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government. Note that the significant changes brought by the Act are to distribute autonomy to the autonomous regions of regencies and cities in the administration of government. In addition, from the format of the philosophy of Regional Government, the enactment of Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government prioritizes the principle of Decentralization. Decentralization is defined as assignment, transfer, or delegation of authority in political, administrative, and financial aspects to lower levels of government [1]. In addition, Maddick in Hoessein also describes the decentralization plan as having 2 (two) interrelated parts, namely the creation of autonomous regions and the delegation of authority by law to deal with areas of special regimes, either detailed or formulated in the usual way. Therefore, decentralization is the autonomy of a citizen who is located in an autonomous area. A citizen who initially did not have an independent position, through decentralization, has an independent position in line with the implementation of an autonomous region. Autonomy, thus handed over by the ruler to the citizens, not to the territory or the ruler of the territory [2].

As a result of granting the widest possible autonomy and authority to the community, is how autonomous regions can improve the ability and efficiency of government administration to accelerate the realization of community welfare through service improvement, empowerment, and community participation in the development process [3]. This condition can be achieved if the autonomous region can improve the quality of regional government administration. In this context, a proper understanding of the meaning and strategy of administrative reform has an important meaning because in the governance of the Region as an autonomous region, it must be able to identify the needs of the community in accelerating the improvement of welfare. This is understandable because administrative reform is a continuous improvement activity that has real goals and is not just an effort at certain and sporadic timeframes for the performance of public zones [4].

From a practical point of view, the implementation of regional autonomy has been greater since 2001 that there has been a change in the arrangement of autonomous regions. This situation motivates autonomous regions to organize important policies that directly increase the basic desires of the people. The paradigm shift in the regime system urges autonomous regions to improve governance skills by creating creative and innovative public policies to always gain public support [5].

The modern administrative approach accommodates the dynamic atmosphere of globalization because it uses a multi-dimensional and disciplined approach in analyzing interrelated internal and external areas. One of the modern administrative approaches is to use an innovative approach in the delivery of public services. This is in line with the governance expected by Indonesia at this time, when referring to a quote from President Joko Widodo's speech when he was elected president at Sentul ICC, Bogor, West Java, Sunday (14/7/2019) in part of

his speech he said: "We must change! We have to change! Again, we have to change. We have to build new values at work, demanding that we adapt quickly to the times. So we must continue to build an adaptive Indonesia, a productive Indonesia, and an innovative Indonesia, a competitive Indonesia." <https://tirto.id/teks-lengkap-pidato-jokowi-sebagai-presiden-terpilih-di-sentul-city-eef9>. The current innovative local government policies can give prominent meaning to the regional autonomy agenda which is still a challenge to be realized.

Based on initial observations and reports in various media, there are several regions in Indonesia that have produced policies that appear to be in favor of the people, including the Surabaya City Government getting an award as the most innovative city in Indonesia at the Innovative Government Award (IGA) virtual performance on Wednesday (29/29/2011). The Surabaya City Government received an IGA in terms of the integrated public service One Gate System between the Population and Civil Registration Service with the Religious Courts as well as with the Surabaya District Court. In addition, in 2018 the Population and Civil Registration Office of the Surabaya City Government has also been awarded the Top 99 Public Service Innovations for 6 in 1 public service innovations which include the processing of birth certificates, deaths, marriages, divorces, moving letters coming in and moving out online. This is where researchers are interested in conducting research on how to model the implementation of public services for the Surabaya City Government with innovation pastoralism.

Previous Research

The results of previous research studies also show that the implementation of regional autonomy has not resulted in the quality of public services expected by the community. As stated by [6] in his research entitled the quality of public services at the Regional Government Representative Office of Tolitoli Regency in Palu City, he stated that the quality of public services is still not good in terms of tangibles and reliability dimensions. This proves that the administrative reforms implemented have not been able to produce good governance, so they have not been able to create good governance that can boost the performance capability of public services. The implementation of the quality of public services on the officer's responsibility variable is the variable that most influences the implementation of the quality of public services [7].

In addition, [8] in this study discusses innovation in the implementation of public services in the health and emergency sector, namely the Public Safety Center (PSC) 119 Bantul Regency. The results of the research show that the PSC service is of good enough quality. PSCs have advantages in providing health and emergency services, namely the ease of accessing these services, by simply calling the toll-free number 119 or local telephone number (0274) 2811119. Research on public services in a collaborative approach shows that stakeholders are the government, citizens, the private sector, and NGOs on organizational, managerial and cultural aspects to support the development of public services [9]. The previous research that has been described is a differentiating indicator that emphasizes that this research is a research on best practice public service delivery with an innovative approach.

Method

This research uses a qualitative research approach, the research design is a case study in accordance with the main questions regarding how [10]. The reason for choosing the case study that is the focus of this research is the implementation of public services in the Surabaya City Government through an innovation approach. The focus of this study is in line with the statement [10]. Whereas case study research is designed for studies that are used to answer phenomena, by developing an in-depth analysis of a program or process. The first step in this research is to identify the existence of an innovation program in the implementation of public services in the Surabaya City Government through online and print media. The second step is coding and analyzing primary data and secondary data obtained from data findings in the field.

Results and Discussion

Innovation is a modern administrative approach to accommodate the dynamic atmosphere of globalization. The Surabaya City Government received an award as the most innovative city in Indonesia at a virtual Innovative Government Award (IGA) performance on Wednesday (29/12/2021), the Surabaya City Government received an IGA in terms of integrated public services, One Gate System between the Population and Civil Registration Service and Religious Courts as well as with the Surabaya District Court. In addition, in previous years, the Surabaya City Government has also spawned many innovations in the implementation of public services.

The Surabaya City Government produced a policy on pro-community public service innovation, namely the "Cak Emus" program which stands for Cangkrukan Young Entrepreneur Surabaya, for which this program received an award in the Public Service Innovation System from the Ministry of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform in 2019. Previously in 2018 the Surabaya City Government has also received 3 (three) Public Service Innovation System awards, namely the innovation "TAHU PANAS (Tak Takut Kehujan, Tak Takut Kepanasan)" which is an activity to repair uninhabitable houses through social rehabilitation programs for slum areas, service innovation units public from the Surabaya City Government Social Service. Furthermore, the City Development Planning Agency of the Surabaya City Government with its innovations, namely Economic Heroes and Young Fighters. This innovation is focused on empowering housewives from poor

families and young fighters. The goal of the economic hero is to reduce the poor to get out of the shackles of poverty. Meanwhile, the Young Fighters are intended for young people who drop out of school or do not continue at the tertiary level, but still have the will for better economic access. (Announcement of Top 99 Public Service Innovations of the Ministry of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform).

The third innovation in 2018 is the 6 in 1 public service innovation which includes the management of birth certificates, death, marriage, divorce, moving letters coming and moving out online at the Population and Civil Registration Office of the Surabaya City Government. The 6 in 1 innovation was initiated to reduce the volume of queues for requests for public services at the Department of Population and Civil Registration, and brokers who open up illegal levies, as well as reduce the processing time of files, so that people can take care of them without having to come to the Population and Civil Registration Office. but only with the e-Lampid application, the public can immediately take care of public services in the field of administration, including the processing of birth certificates, death, marriage, divorce, moving and moving letters. (Announcement of Top 99 Public Service Innovations of the Ministry of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform).

With the 6 in 1 innovation carried out by the Surabaya City Government Population and Civil Registration Service, it also has a positive impact on the Community Satisfaction Index of the Surabaya City Government Population and Civil Registration Service, as contained in table 1 as follows:

Table 1: Community Satisfaction Index Value
Department of Population and Civil Registration of Surabaya City Government

Service Component	Community Satisfaction Index (Year)		
	2017	2018	2019
Terms of Service	79,31	87,81	81,80
Service Systems, Mechanisms, and Procedures	80,73	83,33	80,96
Service Time	71,39	83,55	80,61
Service Fee	78,89	85,26	
Service Officer Competence	79,09	84,82	82,70
Service Officer Behavior	79,48	84,30	82,83
Facilities and infrastructure		83,33	82,02
Handling Complaints, Suggestions, Feedback	75,20	81,27	82,36
Product/Service Results	78,28		81,63
amount	77,80	84,21	81,86

Source: Community Satisfaction Index Survey Report Year 2017, 2018, 2019

In 2018 there was a significant increase in the value of the Community Satisfaction Index, namely the Community Satisfaction Index value of 84.21, an increase of 6.41 from the value of the Community Satisfaction Index in 2017 which received a Community Satisfaction Index value of 77.80. While in 2019 the Population and Civil Registration Office of the Surabaya City Government got a Community Satisfaction Index value of 81.86, a decrease of 2.35 compared to 2018, however, the Community Satisfaction Index of the Surabaya City Government Population and Civil Registration Service in 2019 was still included in the service quality category B (Good).

Based on the research results that have been described, it is identified that the Surabaya City Government has implemented policies that favor the community, namely through public service innovation programs in improving the quality of public services and public welfare. The Surabaya City Government Innovation Program, namely 1) The innovation program "Cak Emus" innovation program stands for Cangkrukan Young Entrepreneur Surabaya, 2) The innovation program "TAHU PANAS (Tak Takut Kehujanan, Tak Takut Kepanasan)" is an activity to repair uninhabitable houses through social rehabilitation programs slum areas, 3) The Economic Heroes and Young Fighters innovation program is an activity to empower housewives from poor families and young people who drop out of school or do not continue at the tertiary level, but still have the will for better economic access. 4) 6 in 1 public service innovation program which includes the management of birth certificates, death, marriage, divorce, moving letters coming and moving out online at the Department of Population and Civil Registration of the Surabaya City Government. For public service innovation 6 in 1, the Surabaya City Government implements strategies, namely 1) utilizing the development of information and communication technology, 2) forming a team consisting of several Regional Apparatus Organizations, 3) developing implementing capabilities 4) encouraging increasing public involvement, 5) increasing efficiency and effectiveness of public services.

Conclusion

That the Surabaya City Government has had many innovations in the implementation of public services to improve public services and welfare. The innovations carried out by the Surabaya Government are 1) "Cak Emus" innovation program 2) "TAHU PANAS" innovation program is an activity to repair uninhabitable houses through social rehabilitation programs in slum areas, 3) Economic Heroes and Young Fighters innovation program is an activity for empowering mothers households from poor families and young people who drop out of school or do not continue at the tertiary level, but still have the will for better economic access. 4) "6 in 1" public service innovation program which includes the management of birth certificates, death, marriage, divorce, moving letters coming and moving out online at the Department of Population and Civil Registration of the Surabaya City Government. For public service innovation "6 in 1", the Surabaya City Government implements strategies, namely 1) utilizing the development of information and communication technology, 2) forming a team consisting of several Regional Apparatus Organizations, 3) developing implementing capabilities 4) encouraging increasing public involvement, 5) increasing efficiency and effectiveness of public services.

Recommendations

The rapid development of technology is an indicator that the government must be more responsive and adaptive to always provide the best public services by utilizing this technology. The Surabaya City Government is expected to always make new innovations in line with the high demands of the community for excellent public services. The Surabaya City Government must always increase community involvement in the process of providing public services.

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